

Power BI app for Tolerance Intervals and Reduced Major Axis Regression

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Abstract

In-line inspection (ILI) tools that run internally in the pipe detect and characterize threats on a pipeline but are prone to inherent variability. The results of these ILI surveys are used to assess the criticality of reported anomalies, but the ILI runs should be compared to actual field excavations among other comparisons. To effectively manage the threats, correlation between ILI runs, and correlation between ILI and Field excavation results are important. Key to assessing how well results compare are tolerance intervals that, with a specified confidence level, cover a given proportion of the population. In this Power BI (PBI) bias assessment app 95% confidence and 80% population coverage is used. This meshes well with industry requirements. Another new added feature is least squares regression. However, often a better result for error prone data is reduced major axis regression. Both regression approaches are used to assess the relative fits of the various data types in the model.

These enhancements have been added to a PBI bias assessment app to provide solid quality results for pipeline companies. This study used representative ILI results to create interactive, statistical, and visual analyses

Key Words: ILI, pipeline, correlation, oil, RMA, tolerance

1. Overview of Power BI bias app

This paper builds on an earlier JSM publication on a Power BI (PBI) bias app (Harper et al, 2022) that covered in detail all the aspects available at that time. Changes have been made over time (e.g., migrating to the 3rd edition of API 1163) to the bias app, but this paper focuses on the recent updates. Interested parties should read the earlier 2022 publication to obtain a better understanding of what the bias app was developed for and its associated output.

The PBI bias app aspects covered in this publication focus on new PBI pages that include the following:

- Self-healing %.
- Correlation coefficient and Tolerance Intervals.
- Regression: both least-squares and reduced major axis.

Especially for the first of these (self-healing %), in-line inspection (ILI) data needs to be discussed. ILI data is obtained by running an ILI tool (sometimes called a pig) through a oil or gas pipeline. For the bias app, two subsequent ILI data sets are compared. The first is often five years older than the newer ILI run for oil lines with a larger time gap often for natural gas lines. The ILI data is noisy and used to estimate corrosion growth over time. Due to the inherent variability, matched pairs (same location on pipe) theoretically should either exhibit some corrosion growth in the years between the two ILI runs or no growth. Unfortunately, it is not uncommon for a matched pair to

exhibit a physically impossible result where the new ILI depth of corrosion value is less than the earlier matched pair. This implies that the corrosion at the matched location has gotten less deep and is called self-healing in this paper. It is not unusual for matched pairs to be classified as self-healing. The sample pipeline in this paper helps lead to a bias assessment to adjust either the old or new ILI to better represent reality.

Before delving into the new features of the PBI bias app, it is appropriate to provide a brief overview of the bias app. Figure 1 provides an initial look of the tool. Two plots and associated textual summary are given. There has been a 0.95 ratio bias (BiasRatioNew) applied to the Adjusted data given in the right plot and lower textual summary of Figure 1 (highlighted with red line). This multiplies each newer ILI value by 0.95. For the sample data in this paper, only the data that is at least 20% wall thickness (WT) is used, and this is highlighted with red line in Figure 1 at the x Depth and y Depth slicers. The plots depict the matched pairs that fit into a given category such as 1-1 pit matches. Depending on the type of pipe seam as well as the ILI tool used, the sizing specifications vary. The red plot points identify those matched pairs in which the difference in the two Depth values exceed the ILI vendor tolerance and are classified as out of specification. This may be due to corrosion growth over the time interval of the two ILI runs or due to the inherent variability in the ILI measurements. If one selected only Electric Fusion Welded (EFW) or Seamless (SMLS) in the PBI Slicer SeamType, then the out of specification pairs become clearer as SMLS pipe has a larger tolerance than EFW.

The difference between the original (not bias adjusted) and the bias adjusted data is examined by working with the bias adjustment options. The four adjustment tools are in the yellow right rectangle below the Adjusted plot (see Harper et al, 2002 for details) in Figure 1. As mentioned above a 0.95 ratio bias assessment on the new ILI is used in this paper.

Figure 1: PBI bias app page with 0.95 ratio bias adjustment to the newer ILI run

1.1 Self-Healing

The pits are matched between the two ILI runs. The newer ILI in theory should only report at least as deep calls than the earlier ILI. The data is noisy, and it is not surprising that some matches appear to show that corrosion appears to be less deep over time. The Self-Healing % in Figure 2 quantifies the percentage that have the older ILI depths deeper than the most recent ILI given any bias adjustment in either ILI data set.

Depending on the tool used, the ILI vendor specifications vary but it is common to assume 80% (often called certainty in pipeline documents) of the ILI calls should be within +/- 10% wall thickness (WT) of a matched field depth. One issue is that the Field measurements are also subject to error. The assumption is often that the matches (depending on seam type) are anticipated to be within +/- 10% WT for ILI to ILI matches also.

Figure 2: Self-healing % for Sample Pipeline

1.2 Tolerance Intervals

As seen in Figure 3, DNV’s PBI bias assessment app computes tolerance interval for both delta and ratio bias. Delta bias is the direct difference between the matched pair. This is similar in some sense to using the standard paired t-test. In such one is testing the null hypothesis that the population difference between the matched pairs equals 0.0. In the application of the bias app, many engineers prefer a ratio bias assessment in which case the expected population ratio used in the null hypothesis is not 0.0 but 1.0 indicating no difference. The below text puts this into the hypothesis testing format with H_0 and H_a being the respective null and alternative hypotheses.

Delta bias

$H_0: \mu_{diff} = 0$ versus $H_a: \mu_{diff} \neq 0$ where μ_{diff} is the population mean of the paired differences

Ratio bias

$H_0: \mu_{ratio} = 1$ versus $H_a: \mu_{ratio} \neq 1$ where μ_{ratio} is the population mean of the paired ratios

Tolerance intervals (Harper, Nenciu, 2023) are for individual observations and not population parameters such as the population mean. The Figure 3 tolerance intervals are 80% population coverage at 95% confidence. If the delta tolerance interval contains 0.0, this indicates no obvious violation that the population does not include 0.0. In a similar vein the ratio tolerance interval should include 1.0 indicating the population of ratios (not the mean) is following what is anticipated. Figure 3 meets both tolerance interval conditions (includes 0 for delta bias, 1 for ratio bias) for all three of the Sources used as labels in the text rows below the plots.

Figure 3: Tolerance Intervals for Sample Pipeline

1.3 Least-Squares and Reduced Major Axis Regression

When both the independent and dependent variables are subject to error, then a key assumption of least squares regression is violated. Least squares regression assumes only the dependent variable has error and that the independent variable has 0 error. Reduced major axis regression explicitly addresses the error in both variables and is often felt to provide an improved regression (Bohonak, 2004; AI Overview, 2025).

Power BI does not currently provide a function for the Pearson correlation coefficient. One can implement the correlation coefficient using a quick Power BI function (Kingpin, 2018) or as done in this paper using the LINEST table function (Olatunde, 2024). Using the LINEST table function one can obtain the Pearson correlation coefficient r and the least square regression intercept and slope coefficients. Converting least-squares regression coefficients to RMA coefficients (Harper, 2016) produces the equations shown in Figure 4 where the subscripts LS and RMA indicate least-squares or reduced major axis accordingly.

$$b_{1(RMA)} = \frac{b_{1(LS)}}{|r|} \quad b_{0(RMA)} = \bar{Y} - b_{1(RMA)}\bar{X}$$

Figure 4: RMA regression coefficients from least-squares regression coefficients

The application of the least-squares to RMA regression coefficients is shown for the sample pipeline in Figure 5 showing the PBI page with these results.

Figure 5: Least Squares and Reduced Major Axis Regression

Summary

This JSM paper discusses recent changes in a Power BI bias app explained in depth in a 2022 JSM proceedings (Harper et al, 2022). To fully understand the logic and methodology underlying bias assessment, the reader is encouraged to read the 2022 article.

The recent updates to the Power BI bias app were introduced in this paper are as follows.

- Self-healing %.
- Correlation coefficient and Tolerance Intervals.
- Regression: both least-squares and reduced major axis.

These topics were discussed in three separate sections of this paper. Interested parties are encouraged to contact the author to further share thoughts.

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